

Performance-based Development of a 3D-printable Strain-hardening Cementitious Composite to Mitigate Girder End Cracks

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Abstract:

Pretensioned concrete bridge girders with thin and deep webs are susceptible to anchorage-zone cracking during prestress release due to the transfer of large prestressing forces over short lengths and the limited tensile capacity of conventional concrete. These cracks pose a durability concern by facilitating moisture and chloride ingress, potentially accelerating corrosion of prestressing steel. This study proposes a materials-based mitigation strategy that replaces localized macro-cracking with distributed micro-cracking by applying a 3D-printed ductile concrete cover at prestress anchorage zones. A performance-based framework integrating structural analysis, material design, and fabrication constraints was developed. Nonlinear finite element analysis was employed to quantify strain demands and establish target mechanical properties for the anchorage zone. A 3D-printable strain-hardening cementitious composite (SHCC) was then developed through iterative material tailoring and laboratory testing to meet both hardened-state mechanical property requirements and fresh-state rheological property requirements necessary for extrusion-based printing. Results indicate that effective crack mitigation requires a tensile strain capacity of 0.6% or higher, which can be achieved using SHCC. Printability was found to depend on a narrow range of rheological properties characterized by the flowability factor and flow reduction rate. For the available pumping and printing system, flowability factor between 1.2 and 1.5 and flow reduction rate of 20% or higher per hour for the first 30 minutes were identified as suitable ranges. The proposed approach provides a practical pathway for integrating advanced cementitious materials into precast girders, improving crack control and enhancing long-term durability without altering conventional construction practices.

1. Introduction

Precast, pretensioned concrete bridge girders are widely used in modern highway infrastructure due to their structural efficiency, rapid construction, and cost-effectiveness. However, these girders are susceptible to anchorage-zone cracking during prestress release. The transfer of large prestressing forces from steel strands to the surrounding concrete occurs over a short length near the girder ends, generating high, localized tensile strains. Combined with the inherently brittle behavior and low tensile strain capacity of conventional concrete, this often results in cracking, as shown in Figure 1 (Okumus et al., 2016). These cracks can facilitate moisture and chloride ingress, accelerating corrosion of prestressing steel.

Figure 1. (a) End cracks in a pretensioned bulb tee girder (Okumus et al., 2016) (b) 3D-printed SHCC covers as permanent formwork at girder ends

To address this limitation, this study proposes a materials-based strategy using 3D-printed strain-hardening cementitious composite (SHCC) covers at girder ends. This approach is implemented in two steps: (i) 3D printing the covers in advance and allowing them to fully cure and harden, and (ii) using the hardened covers as permanent formwork within the removable girder formwork at the precast facility. Bonding between the SHCC cover and the cast concrete develops progressively as the core concrete hardens. The SHCC cover acts as both permanent formwork and a crack-control layer, enabling distributed microcracking instead of localized macrocracking. This approach limits the use of advanced concrete materials to critical regions while maintaining compatibility with conventional precast construction.

2. Target Material Properties

A finite element model (FEM) was developed in ABAQUS (Dassault Systèmes, 2023) to simulate anchorage-zone cracking. The model was calibrated using experimental data from O’Callaghan and Bayrak (2008), including reinforcement strain measurements after prestress release. The response of a Tx70 girder was simulated. The validated model enabled quantification of strain demands in the anchorage zone and provided a basis for defining target material properties for the SHCC cover.

The SHCC performance requirements were categorized into fresh-state and hardened-state properties. Hardened-state targets were derived from FEM results, while fresh-state requirements were defined based on the demands of mixing, pumping, extrusion, and layering. These processes impose conflicting rheological requirements. To quantify rheological behavior, the flow table test (ASTM C1437) was used to determine two parameters: (i) flowability factor and (ii) flow reduction rate, similar to Soltan and Li (2018). The flowability factor represents initial workability, while the flow reduction rate captures thixotropic behavior over time. These parameters were used to define a narrow printability window for SHCC mixtures.

3. Development of Trial Mix Designs

A previously developed SHCC mixture by Fakhri et al. (2019) with high ductility but poor printability was used as the baseline, and modified iteratively to achieve the required printability. The water-to-cementitious materials ratio (w/cm) was reduced from 0.38 to 0.31 to reduce flow and enhance strength, while the PVA fiber length was shortened from 12 mm to 8 mm to improve pumping and extrusion characteristics. Additionally, the dosages of high-range water-reducing admixture (HRWRA) and viscosity-modifying admixture (VMA) were adjusted to achieve the target rheological behavior. A total of sixteen trial mixtures were prepared and evaluated based on flowability factor and flow reduction rate. Four mixtures were shortlisted for further optimization. These selected mixtures were subsequently refined by incorporating microsilica, ground silica, and Type III cement to enhance thixotropic behavior. Ultimately, three mixtures were identified as suitable for 3D printing applications.

4. Evaluation of Fresh and Hardened Properties

Fresh-state screening involved both qualitative and quantitative assessments to evaluate printability. Fiber dispersion was examined manually to ensure the absence of clumping, while extrudability was assessed using a caulking gun with a 0.76" nozzle. Buildability was evaluated by stacking multiple layers and observing shape retention under self-weight. Flow table tests were conducted immediately after mixing and again after 30 minutes to quantify flow reduction over time and identify any segregation or bleeding. The rheological requirements at various stages, from mixing to printing of SHCC, are shown in Figure 2. Hardened properties were subsequently evaluated through compressive strength testing (ASTM C109), direct tension tests (Fakhri et al., 2019), and four-point bending tests (ASTM C78).

Figure 2. Rheological requirements at various stages, from mixing to printing of SHCC

5. Results

Finite element analysis indicated a maximum tensile strain of approximately 0.32% at the girder end surface, leading to the establishment of a target tensile strain capacity exceeding 0.6% to account for material variability and ensure effective crack mitigation. Representative FEM and surface principal tensile strain profile at the girder end with SHCC cover are shown in Figure 3. Furthermore, the incorporation of a 0.75" thick SHCC cover was found to have minimal impact on internal reinforcement stresses in the numerical model. To ensure printability, the required fresh-state properties were identified as a flowability factor in the range of 1.2–1.5 and a flow reduction rate of at least 20% per hour for the first 30 minutes.

Figure 3. (a) FEM (b) Surface principal tensile strain contours at girder end with SHCC cover

Among the finalized mixtures, all three satisfied both flowability and mechanical performance requirements, with compressive strengths of 7.5–8.5 ksi and tensile strain capacities of at least 0.6%. The flow reduction rate for Mix1 was slightly below the established performance target, allowing a longer waiting time before printing, whereas Mix2 and Mix3 are suitable for printing shortly after mixing. A summary of the test results for these three mixtures is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Fresh-state and Hardened-state properties of 3D printable SHCC mixtures

Mix	Flowability factor (avg)	Flow reduction rate (% per hour)	Compressive strength, ksi (Mpa)	Tensile strain capacity (%)
Mix1	1.4	19	7.5 (52)	0.7
Mix2	1.3	20	8.5 (59)	0.6
Mix3	1.4	21	8.2 (57)	0.9
Performance Target	1.2-1.5	≥ 20	≥ 6.0 (42)	≥ 0.6

6. Conclusions

This study demonstrates a performance-based design of a 3D-printable strain-hardening cementitious composite to mitigate anchorage-zone cracking in prestressed concrete girders. The key conclusions are as follows:

1. Effective crack mitigation requires SHCC with tensile strain capacity greater than or equal to 0.6% as demonstrated for the example prestressed girder.
2. A narrow rheological window governs the printability of SHCC, quantified in this study by a flowability factor (1.2–1.5) and a flow reduction rate ($\geq 20\%$ per hour).
3. Iterative mixture optimization, including adjustments to w/cm ratio, fiber length, and admixture content, can be used for achieving both printability and mechanical performance simultaneously.

SHCC mixtures meeting both fresh-state and hardened-state requirements are successfully achieved. These mixtures are suitable for extrusion-based 3D printing and can be considered for structural applications as covers.

7. References

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